

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through
Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

A Study of Motivation in Foundries of Kolhapur District

Mrs Madhuri Prakash Rasal

Research Student, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

Organised By:

Management Department, Chhatrapati
Shahu Institute of Business Education
and Research, Kolhapur, Maharashtra

An Autonomous Institute Under UGC & Shivaji University
College with Potential for Excellence (CPE) - III Phase.

How to cite this paper: Mrs Madhuri Prakash Rasal " A Study of Motivation in Foundries of Kolhapur District" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Special Issue | Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through Interdisciplinary

Practices in Management, March 2019, pp.142-144, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23086.pdf>

IJTSRD23086

Motivation encourages the employees to give their best efforts to achieve the goals. Motivation makes person energetic to work hard towards the goal oriented. Thus when a manager wants from employees to work has then he has to motivate them for their better performance. Manager must try to motivate employee by satisfying their need. In modern days need satisfaction is dependent upon organization effectiveness, growth and success. Higher the effectiveness higher will be the satisfaction. Organization effectiveness is also called as success, growth, efficiency, productivity and profitability. Foundry can be said effective if its is able to achieve maximum goals within available resources. (Lillis J. C. 1985).

Objectives of the study

1. To analyse the motivation methods followed by manager in foundry industry.
2. To analyse the effect of motivation methods on organization effectiveness.
3. To find out conclusion and suggestions.

ABSTRACT

Employee motivation is the force acting on or within a person that causes the person to behave in a specific goal directed manner. The motivation process has become a principal need of organizations, managers because employee motivation will be the deciding factor in work performance, success or failure of an organization. (Samuel and Chipunza, 2009). "Foundry is a factory that produces metal casting. Metals are cast into different shapes by melting them into liquid, pouring into moulds and remove moulds. Kolhapur is one of the develop city, foundry industry plays important role in its development. Different types of motivation techniques are followed by managers to get the work done by them. It leads the foundries towards the success. Managerial skills and motivation methods can improve the performance of employees and increase organization profit. So researcher has decided to study motivation methods followed by different types of foundry industries and its effect on organization effectiveness.

KEYWORDS: Motivation, Foundry Industry, Effectiveness, Managers, Employees, motives

INTRODUCTION

Manager always try to coordinate the various factors like human beings and machines etc. to make proper use of technology and machinery. It is important to improve the efficiency of human beings. Manager has to improve the performance of employees. It is depends upon the ability of perform and motivation. Even if the employee is having the ability to work but if he has not properly motivated by the manager then he will not perform well.

Statement of Problems

The success of any organization is based on individual and group performance. Human behaviors are generally related with the thoughts, feelings, emotions, motives and needs etc. large no of persons are working in foundry organization. Foundry success is depending upon the employees performance. To get the work done from employee managers has to use different motivation methods to motivate them to work hard to achieve predefined foundry objectives.

Significance of the study

Present study is mainly concerned with study of motivation methods followed by manager in foundry industry. Motivation factor is responsible for organization success and organization effectiveness. So researcher selected this topic to know the importance and befits of motivation methods which can improve the organization growth this study is helpful to improve relationship between manager and workers and to know which motivation method should be follow to influence employees behavior.

Scope of the study

The study is about selected foundries in Kolhapur foundry cluster. It has limited to five years period from 2010-2015. It has focus on human resource function of motivation.

Research methodology

Primary data has been collected through structured questionnaires from employees and secondary data has been collected from journals, magazines, reports of state and central government, web site and profile of foundry industry. There are around 300 foundry industries according to Kolhapur foundry cluster. It is decided to visit 5% units it happened to be 15 foundry units. each foundry is considered as strata under the study. The total no of employees working in selected foundry units are 1195. they visited by following stratified random sampling method. To find out sample size estimated and respective employees were contracted using simple random sampling method by formula given by Kothari after the calculation sample size for the study is 420.

Data analysis and interpretation

For the study of motivation methods scale is used given by shouksmith and Geoge and various variable used are helpfulness, reward giving, opportunity giving, job status, job security, working condition, appreciation.

Hypothesis of study

H0: employee motivation is independent of their type of employment.

H0: employee motivation is independent of level in organization

H0: employee motivation is independent of employee perception of salary

H0: employees motivation is independent of education.

Employee motivation

Here level of employees motivation is assessed by adapting the scale of Shouksmith Geoge. A construct validation of scale for measuring work motivation. New Zeland Journal of Psychology.

Statement	Mean score	Rank
Has managers and leaders who are helpful and fair	3.32	10
Allows you to reach and develop your full potential	3.33	9
Provides satisfactory material reward	3.42	8
Is a challenging and exciting job	3.42	7
Gives you status and prestige	3.43	6
Takes all round and considering all its aspects is a very good one	3.43	5
Is a secure one	3.44	4
Provides good physical working conditions	3.48	3
Means working in pleasant and helpful environment	3.53	2
Is one where your good work and hard effort are appreciated	3.59	1
Total mean score	3.40	

Employee Motivation Against Demographics

Hypothesis	Test	P Value	Result
H0: employee motivation is independent of their types of employment.	Mann-Whitney U	.000	< 0.05 Reject
H0: Employee motivation is independent of level in organization	Mann-Whitney U	.000	< 0.005 Reject
H0: Employee motivation is independent of employee perception of salary	Kruskal Wallis Test	.966	> 0.05 Accept
H0: Employee motivation is independent of education	Kruskal Wallis test	.000	< 0.05 Reject

Findings

1. Overall employee motivation score is 3.40, it indicate that employees are not highly motivated or de-motivated also.
2. Score on develop full potential of the employees is least, it indicate that employees have a opinion the present employment does not playing active role in developing and offering full potential of the employees.
3. Full time employed employee are comparatively more motivated than contractual employees.
4. Employees working on managerial level are more motivated comparing to the employees who are working on ground level in the organization.
5. The salary is not only one of the important factors for the motivation.
6. Motivation of employees changes as per the education level. The employees having more education than graduations are highly motivated than the employees having education level less that graduation.

Conclusion

Motivations one of the important elements in the directing function, by motivating the workers manager directs or guides the action into desired direction for accomplishing the goals for the organization. Organization effectiveness can be achieved only through the motivation process as motivation contributes to make foundry to create a good relation between workers and managers. Motivation is the best remedy for making new changes. If the workers of an organization are motivated they will accepts and ready to implement the changes heartily and this help to keep the organization on the track of progress. From the research it has concluded that ground level employees shall be motivated through some non monetary benefits such as offering positions as team leaders, best performer and providing needed facilities like transportation or accommodation to attach them with the industry. Leadership is not only one facto to create the organization progress, some other motivational techniques like self-motivation, training for individual should be apply for organizational growth.

References

- [1] Ashwaathappa k. (1995) Essential of Business Environment. Bombay Himalaya Publishing House.
- [2] Stogdil R. M. (1948). Personnel Factors Associates with Leadership. Presntice hall Publication.
- [3] Yukl Gary (1981) Leadership in Organization, eagkewol cliffis N. J. Prenticehall.
- [4] Rao Subba P (2001), Personnel and Resource Management, Himalaya Publilshing.
- [5] Samuel, M. and Chipnuza, C. (2009) Employee Relation and Turnover using Motivational Variables as a Panacea pp. 410-415.
- [6] shouksmith G. (1989) Shouksmith Geoge a Consturct Validatin of a Scale for Measuring Work Motivation. New Zealand Journal of Psychology, 76-81.
- [7] Basotia G. K. (2003), Human Resource Management, Shree Niwas Publication.
- [8] Sinha K. P. 7 D. P. Geol (2002), Foundry Technology, Standard publication distributors.
- [9] P. Jain 1st July 2015, Principles of Foundry Mc graw hill education 3rd edition.
- [10] Manappa Arun and Saiyadian mirza (1996) Personnel Management, New Delhi Tata Mc. Hill publishing.

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

